

Orthogonal beams and codebook design for near-field space division multiple access in 6G systems

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Abstract—Space division multiple access (SDMA), a powerful method routinely applied in multi-user multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) communications, relies on the angular orthogonality of beams in the far field, to distinguish multiple users at different angles. Yet, with the gradual shift of wireless connectivity to the near-field of large radiating apertures, the applicability of classical SDMA becomes questionable. Recently proposed near-field multiple access schemes employ focused beams, which achieve orthogonality only asymptotically with respect to the transmitter (Tx) size. Hence, a multiple access scheme based on beams with strictly zero near-field correlation is still missing. In this work we propose a novel technique, to enable SDMA in the near-field. By judicious design, we select the family of cosine beams and we prove that they satisfy the orthogonality condition for finite-size Tx, offering in the near-field a multitude of communication modes, implemented by beams that can co-exist without interference. We demonstrate analytically that the orthogonality of beams is preserved at any location of the receiver (Rx), from the near-field to the far-field of the Tx and, to test our analytical findings, we propagate the designed beams numerically, and we measure their orthogonality both at the Tx and the Rx. We verify that the orthogonality of the proposed beams is successfully retrieved at an Rx that resides in the near-field of the Tx, and is also robust to displacements of the Rx. We also demonstrate how the correlation of beams generated with uniform linear arrays (ULAs) is extended to uniform planar arrays (UPAs) in a straightforward and insightful manner. Based on our findings, we propose codebook designs for near-field space division multiple access (NF-SDMA) that are applicable for Rx with many elements and even with single antennas.

Index Terms—near field, orthogonality, cosine beams, multiple access, large arrays, wavefront engineering.

I. INTRODUCTION

WIRELESS communications are nowadays shifting to higher frequencies. With increasing frequency the wavelength becomes shorter and, because the size of everyday objects does not change along, several intriguing properties arise. For example, at shorter wavelength λ , a radiating element of size D becomes electrically larger, because the ratio D/λ increases. A direct consequence is that the Fraunhofer distance $z_F = 2D^2/\lambda$ increases, and the near-to-far-field transition is transferred to larger distances, thus enabling operation of communications in the radiating near-field of radiating apertures, such as reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) [1]–[6], large antenna arrays (LAAs) and extremely large-scale antenna arrays (ELAA) equipped with thousands of antennas

[7]–[9].

In view of the high requirements of future wireless connectivity [10], the utilization of frequency bands, such as the mmWave and THz is gradually becoming common ground [11], [12], and the use of large radiating apertures is already being studied for manipulating the wavefront of the radiated wave, to acquire curvature beyond the typical far-field planar form [4], [5], [13]. For example, the concept of beamfocusing is constantly gaining ground as a means to concentrate the power at controllable distances and small areas, a key element for energy efficient communications [14]–[19] and localization applications [20]–[23]. Recently, bending beams [24]–[26] and beams with self-healing properties were proposed as an enabler for perceptive, resilient, and efficient networks [27].

As the possibilities for the formation of new beams with exotic properties beyond conventional beamforming are practically endless, there is a plethora of choices for designing such beams to be orthogonal in the near-field. Orthogonal beams can co-exist without interference, therefore correspond to communication modes, i.e. orthogonal channels between a transmitter (Tx) and a receiver (Rx). Thus, they can be used to significantly enhance the channel capacity, by means of parallel data multiplexing. Engineering the properties of such beams to devise communication modes for near-field multiple access could boost wireless connectivity in the near-field to unprecedented performance levels.

A. Prior works

It is well-known that beam propagation in the far-field is equivalent to Fourier-transforming the beam at its starting location [28]. As a result, the properties of beams in the far-field can be accurately predicted by their design at the Tx. By choosing the appropriate steering vectors in a beamformer, one can tailor the maxima and minima of the corresponding beams in the far-field, to ensure that at the angle of maximum intensity of a certain beam, all other beams have nulls, thus minimizing the interference. This technique refers to the well-known multiple access schemes of space division multiple access (SDMA) [29] and beam division multiple access (BDMA) [30]–[32], which rely on the angular orthogonality of beams in the far-field. A key to the underlying mechanism of SDMA is that, in the far-field, a beam evolves in a self-similar manner; hence, the angular orthogonality holds for any distance from the Tx. In the near-field, however, the same beam is characterized by spatial intensity oscillations

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that change rapidly for different propagation distances. Hence, the classical far-field SDMA fails in near-field situations, and to define orthogonal beams in a similar manner becomes a challenging task.

Along these lines, in [33], it was recently demonstrated how to construct communication modes with focused beams, by taking advantage of the narrow extent of the focal area. The proposed orthogonality ensured minimum interference between beams, similar to how the maxima and minima of beams are treated in the classical far-field SDMA. A near-field non-orthogonal multiple access (NF-NOMA) scheme was proposed in [34], which was based on beamfocusing, applied on users having different angular directions. It was demonstrated that the proposed NF-NOMA scheme improves the spectral efficiency, compared to conventional far-field communications. In [35], [36], the concept of location division multiple access (LDMA) was introduced, employing focused beams. The orthogonality was defined in terms of the inner product of the steering vectors, and it was shown that zero correlation between focused beams can be achieved only asymptotically, i.e. infinitely large arrays are required. Similarly, in [37], beamfocusing-based near-field multiple access schemes were analyzed, leveraging the angular orthogonality and the asymptotic range orthogonality of focused beams. The orthogonality was defined in terms of the inner product of the normalized channels. In [38] it was shown that orbital angular momentum (OAM) can provide the necessary orthogonality for finite-size TxS, to constitute communication modes with focused OAM beams in the near-field.

Evidently, there are various ways to define orthogonality, as also thoroughly discussed in the recent review [39]. In a Hilbert space, two vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are orthogonal when their inner product $\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \rangle = 0$. Adopting this definition to beams in their far-field, it turns out that the angular orthogonality [40], [41] ensures that the peak of each beam coincides with the nulls of all the other beams [42, Chapter 6.3]. Hence, in far-field communications, zero inner product of the steering vectors guarantees beam orthogonality for both multi-antenna and single-antenna RxS. However, in the near-field, the wavefront and intensity of the beam change locally with propagation distance, and it is not clear how beam orthogonality can be achieved for multi-antenna and single-antenna RxS that reside in the near-field.

Importantly, most effort in designing near-field multiple access schemes has been focused on the utilization of focused beams, which are either entirely non-orthogonal [34] or achieve orthogonality only asymptotically [35]–[37]. Hence, a multiple access scheme based on beams, which satisfy the near-field orthogonality criterion, i.e., that have strictly zero correlation, is still missing.

B. Our contributions

In view of the various definitions of orthogonality, and in lack of a near-field multiple access scheme being based on beams that satisfy the orthogonality criterion, in this paper we define beam orthogonality for multi-beam antenna systems and we propose cosine beams as a family of beams satisfying

the near-field orthogonality property, which offers a multitude of communication modes for both multi-antenna and single-antenna RxS. The contributions are summarized as follows:

- We introduce a novel technique for near-field SDMA (NF-SDMA) to bring into the near-field the classical far-field SDMA and its benefits, which are essential for near-field applications in future wireless communications.
- We prove theoretically that the orthogonality of beams is preserved at any location, from the near-field to the far-field of the Tx.
- To design communication modes in the near-field, we select the class of cosine beams that offer strictly zero correlations for TxS of finite size, with respect to all associated parameters, such as the beam direction and beam range. Our selection is inspired by the linearity of the phase shifts required to excite these beams, which is also a key aspect of the far-field SDMA orthogonality.
- We derive analytically the correlations of cosine beams and we provide analytical expressions for the orthogonality condition in ULAs and UPAs.
- We prove theoretically that there is a countable set of orthogonal beams with different beam ranges, all propagating along the same direction. We also prove that the same conclusion holds for beams propagating along different directions with common beam range. Additionally, we demonstrate that there is a multitude of sets of orthogonal beams with different directions and different beam ranges, providing an ideal means for NF-SDMA in both the angular and the distance domain.
- We numerically verify for different array sizes that the orthogonality of cosine beams is successfully retrieved at an Rx that resides in the near-field of the Tx, and is also robust to displacements of the Rx.
- Based on our findings, we propose codebook designs for NF-SDMA that are applicable for RxS with many elements and even with single antennas.

C. Organization and notations

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II we define the condition for beam orthogonality. In Section III we introduce the family of cosine beams and we study their correlations for ULAs. In Section IV we extend the analysis to UPAs. In Section V we propose codebook designs for NF-SDMA for multi-antenna RxS. In Section VI we propose codebook designs for NF-SDMA for single-antenna RxS. In Section VII we summarize the concluding remarks of this work.

Notations: In this paper \mathbb{Z} denotes the set of integers. $[\cdot]^T$ and $[\cdot]^H$ denote the transpose and conjugate-transpose operations, respectively; $[\cdot]$ is the floor function, $|\cdot|$ denotes the norm of its complex argument and the asterisk $*$ denotes the complex conjugate.

II. BEAM ORTHOGONALITY

Let us consider a Tx, such as a uniform planar array (UPA), centered at the origin of the coordinate system, with its surface

Figure 1. Invariance of beam correlations from the near-field to the far-field, explained in k -space. Schematic illustration of two beams propagating from the Tx to the Rx. The footprints of beams 1 and 2 at the Rx, $\hat{E}_{1,R}$ and $\hat{E}_{2,R}$, are expressed in terms of their respective footprints at the Tx, $\hat{E}_{1,T}$ and $\hat{E}_{2,T}$. The correlation of the two beams remains invariant in k -space and, consequently, in real space.

extending on the xy -plane, as shown in Fig. 1. A Rx is located at distance z , with its surface also residing on the xy -plane. The Tx generates beams that propagate along the z -axis, the E -field of which at the observation point $\mathbf{r}=(x, y, z)$ is $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})=\mathbf{E}(x, y, z)$. The correlation of two such beams $\mathbf{E}_1(x, y, z)$, $\mathbf{E}_2(x, y, z)$, as defined in terms of their inner product on the transverse xy -plane, is written as

$$C = \frac{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} E_1(x, y, z) E_2^*(x, y, z) dx dy}{\sqrt{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |E_1(x, y, z)|^2 dx dy} \sqrt{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |E_2(x, y, z)|^2 dx dy}}, \quad (1)$$

where E_1, E_2 are the magnitudes of the E -field vectors. According to Parseval's identity [43], the inner product of E_1, E_2 is given equivalently in k -space via the equality

$$\begin{aligned} \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} E_1(x, y, z) E_2^*(x, y, z) dx dy &= \\ &= \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{E}_1(k_x, k_y; z) \hat{E}_2^*(k_x, k_y; z) dk_x dk_y, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where k_x, k_y are the spatial frequencies corresponding to the Cartesian transverse coordinates, x, y , and the hats denote the waves in Fourier space. Using (2), the beam correlation function can be written in k -space as

$$C = \frac{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{E}_1(k_x, k_y; z) \hat{E}_2^*(k_x, k_y; z) dk_x dk_y}{\sqrt{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\hat{E}_1(k_x, k_y; z)|^2 dk_x dk_y} \sqrt{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\hat{E}_2(k_x, k_y; z)|^2 dk_x dk_y}}. \quad (3)$$

At this point, we can take advantage of the fact that the Fourier spectrum of a beam at distance $z > 0$ can be expressed in terms of its spectrum at $z = 0$, as (see Appendix A for details)

$$\hat{E}(k_x, k_y; z) = \hat{E}(k_x, k_y; 0) e^{jk_z z}, \quad (4)$$

where $k_z = \sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}$ and k is the free-space wavenumber. Using (4), the correlation function (3) takes the form

$$C = \frac{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{E}_1(k_x, k_y; 0) \hat{E}_2^*(k_x, k_y; 0) dk_x dk_y}{\sqrt{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\hat{E}_1(k_x, k_y; 0)|^2 dk_x dk_y} \sqrt{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\hat{E}_2(k_x, k_y; 0)|^2 dk_x dk_y}}, \quad (5)$$

which is *independent of the propagation distance*. Therefore, the correlation calculated at the Tx is preserved along the entire propagation path. This property is of central importance, as it allows us to design beams with the desired correlations at the Tx, guaranteeing that they are also preserved at the Rx, regardless of whether the Rx is in the near- or far-field of the Tx. Of course, in the far-field, the spatial extent of beams is usually much larger than typical antenna sizes and, to retrieve the correlations at the Rx correctly, the integration in (1) would require impractically large Rx's. However, for near-field applications, beams usually have a narrow extent, by design, and can therefore be captured entirely by the Rx. Characteristic examples are focused beams and non-diffracting beams, i.e. beams that propagate with invariant transverse intensity profile. Consequently, we can design such beams with the desired orthogonality at the Tx, and successfully retrieve their correlations at the Rx.

At the Tx, we may limit the integration within its surface, S_T , outside of which the beam is zero, to express (1) as

$$C = \frac{\iint_{S_T} E_1(x, y) E_2^*(x, y) dx dy}{\sqrt{\iint_{S_T} |E_1(x, y)|^2 dx dy} \sqrt{\iint_{S_T} |E_2(x, y)|^2 dx dy}}. \quad (6)$$

For arrays consisting of $N_x \times N_y$ elements, arranged with periodicity d_x and d_y along the x and y directions, respectively, the Cartesian coordinates are discretized, i.e. $x = n_x d_x, y = n_y d_y$ ($n_x, n_y \in \mathbb{Z}$), and (6) takes its discrete form

$$C = \frac{\sum_{n_x} \sum_{n_y} E_1(n_x, n_y) E_2^*(n_x, n_y)}{\sqrt{\sum_{n_x} \sum_{n_y} |E_1(n_x, n_y)|^2} \sqrt{\sum_{n_x} \sum_{n_y} |E_2(n_x, n_y)|^2}}. \quad (7)$$

III. COSINE BEAMS FOR NF-SDMA

In the classical far-field SDMA, steering vectors with linear phase shifts generate beams that, in the far-field, acquire practically flat wavefronts (zero curvature), with the same (linear) phase gradient of the steering vectors that generate them. Hence, the SDMA orthogonality at the Rx is associated with the linear phase shifts at the Tx. Inspired by this property, we select the family of cosine beams, the excitation of which requires linear phase shifts of the form $k\beta|x|$, where β is a real-valued tuning parameter. Following our design principle, next, we prove that cosine beams offer beamsets that satisfy the orthogonality criterion, i.e. $C = 0$, enabling a multitude of communication modes, and opening up vast possibilities for near-field multiple access schemes, such as the concept of near-field space division multiple access (NF-SDMA).

Let us consider a large uniform linear array (ULA), centered at the origin of the coordinate system and extending on the x -axis. The ULA consists of N_x elements with spacing d_x and generates beams with tailored amplitude and phase characteristics that propagate on the xz -plane, as shown in Fig. 2. The E -field at the input plane ($z = 0$) can be described by the general form

$$E(x, 0, 0) = A(x) e^{j\phi(x)}, \quad (8)$$

where A is the amplitude and ϕ the phase.

A cosine beam is formed by the superposition of two

Figure 2. Cosine beams for NF-SDMA. (a) Ray representation. The shaded triangular region marks the beam content within the cosine beam range, the latter extending from the ULA up to distance z_{\max} . (b) Intensity of equivalent numerically propagated beam, using an array of size $N_x = 1000$. The operation frequency is 150 GHz ($\lambda = 2$ mm) and $d_x = \lambda/2$, here and throughout all the examples in this work. (c) System model for ULA communication systems, depicting two cosine beams with parameters θ, z_{\max} and $\theta_{\text{ref}}, z_{\max, \text{ref}}$, respectively. The shaded regions mark the beam content enclosed by the outer rays of each beam, as denoted in (a).

waves traveling at opposite oblique angles [44], [45]. A straightforward way to implement such beams is to introduce linear phase shifts with opposite slope around $x = 0$, while keeping uniform amplitude (constant A). Hence, for steering taking place on the xz -plane, we may consider the following phase profile at the input plane

$$\phi(x) = kx \sin \theta - k\beta_x |x|, \quad (9)$$

where θ is the steering angle, i.e., a global angle, along which the entire beam is directed, and β_x is a constant, associated with the slope of the two counter-propagating constituents of the beam. Note that, for $\beta_x = 0$, (9) accounts for conventional beam steering. The form of the $k\beta_x|x|$ term expresses the fact that parts of the beam that reside at opposite sides of the ULA (with respect to its center) have in-plane k -components with opposite signs. In the equivalent ray representation, this corresponds to rays with opposite slopes, namely $(1/k)(\partial\phi/\partial x) = \pm\beta_x$ with respect to the z -axis, as shown schematically in Fig. 2(a). Due to the opposite slopes, the rays converge and overlap within a rhombic area, where

a standing wave is formed. This area is enclosed by the outer rays (rays starting from the edges of the ULA), which intersect at a maximum distance z_{\max} , before they continue propagating individually towards opposite directions. Therefore, the parameter β_x simply controls the beam convergence and, as we show in the Appendix B, it is associated with the distance z_{\max} as

$$\beta_x = \frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max}}. \quad (10)$$

The distance z_{\max} marks the cosine beam range, i.e. the propagation distance for which the standing wave is formed in the transverse (xy) plane, as shown in the ray representation in Fig. 2(a) and also in the numerically propagated beam in Fig. 2(b). Here and throughout all the examples in this work, the operation frequency is 150 GHz ($\lambda = 2$ mm) and $d_x = \lambda/2$.

The corresponding steering vector that generates cosine beams can be constructed by expressing (9) at points $x = n_x d_x$, i.e. by discretizing the continuous phase on the ULA grid. The discretized version of the phase acquires the form

$$\phi(n_x) = kd_x n_x \sin \theta - kd_x \beta_x |n_x|, \quad (11)$$

where

$$n_x = -\frac{N_x - 1}{2}, -\frac{N_x - 1}{2} + 1, \dots, \frac{N_x - 1}{2}. \quad (12)$$

Hence, the steering vector that imposes the phase profile (11) on the elements of the ULA, is given by

$$\mathbf{a}(\theta, \beta_x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_x}} \left[e^{j\phi(-\frac{N_x-1}{2})}, e^{j\phi(-\frac{N_x-1}{2}+1)}, \dots, e^{j\phi(\frac{N_x-1}{2})} \right]^T. \quad (13)$$

A. Beam correlations at the Tx

Consider a cosine beam with tunable parameters θ, z_{\max} , and a reference cosine beam with fixed parameters $\theta_{\text{ref}}, z_{\max, \text{ref}}$, as depicted in Fig. 2(c). The correlation (7) of the two beams can be equivalently expressed in terms of their steering vectors as $C = \mathbf{a}(\theta, z_{\max})^H \mathbf{a}(\theta_{\text{ref}}, z_{\max, \text{ref}})$ (see Appendix C for details). The magnitude of C is

$$C_L(w_\theta, w_z) = \left| \frac{1}{N_x} \sum_{n_x} e^{jw_\theta n_x} e^{jw_z |n_x|} \right|, \quad (14)$$

where the subscript L indicates that the correlation function refers to linear arrays, and

$$w_\theta = kd_x (\sin \theta_{\text{ref}} - \sin \theta), \quad (15a)$$

$$w_z = kd_x (\beta_x - \beta_{x, \text{ref}}) = kd_x \left(\frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max}} - \frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max, \text{ref}}} \right), \quad (15b)$$

express the angular detuning and beam range detuning, respectively, between the two beams. Before investigating the general expression (14), we will first analyze two characteristic special cases, namely $w_\theta = 0, w_z \neq 0$ and $w_\theta \neq 0, w_z = 0$.

Figure 3. Correlation of cosine beams for $w_\theta = 0$ or $w_z = 0$. (a),(b) Beams with $w_\theta = 0$, i.e., propagating along the same direction ($\theta = \theta_{\text{ref}}$) and converging at different distance ($z_{\text{max}} \neq z_{\text{max,ref}}$). (c),(d) Beams with $w_z = 0$, i.e., propagating along different directions ($\theta \neq \theta_{\text{ref}}$) and converging at the same distance ($z_{\text{max}} = z_{\text{max,ref}}$). (a),(c) Global plots of C_L for variable ULA size as a function of the detuning parameters. (b),(d) Examples for ULA with $N_x = 500$ elements. The color plots are depicted in logarithmic scale, to emphasize the details.

1) *Beams with $w_\theta = 0$ and $w_z \neq 0$* : This case corresponds to beams that propagate along the same direction (zero angular detuning), $\theta = \theta_{\text{ref}}$, with different beam ranges, $z_{\text{max}} \neq z_{\text{max,ref}}$. For $w_\theta = 0$, the summation in (14) takes the simple form

$$C_L(0, w_z) = \left| \frac{1}{N_x} \sum_{n_x} e^{jw_z |n_x|} \right| = \left| \frac{\sin\left(\frac{N_x}{4} w_z\right)}{\frac{N_x}{2} \sin\left(\frac{1}{2} w_z\right)} \right|. \quad (16)$$

The solutions of equation $C_L(0, w_z) = 0$ satisfy

$$w_z = \frac{4\pi p}{N_x}, \quad (17)$$

where $p \in \mathbb{Z}$, with $p \neq 0, \pm N_x/2, \pm 2N_x/2, \dots$, to exclude the nulls of the denominator that lead to $C_L(0, w_z) = 1$. While w_z can mathematically acquire any value, for practical applications, where $z_{\text{max}} > N_x d_x/2$, (15b) dictates that $w_z < kd_x$. According to (17), this translates into $|p| < N_x kd_x/4\pi$, and hence $0 < |p| < N_x kd_x/4\pi$.

In Fig.3(a) we plot $C_L(0, w_z)$ as a function of the array size N_x and the normalized detuning parameter $\beta_x - \beta_{x,\text{ref}} = w_z/kd_x$, showing the first few branches within the range $p = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm 18$. Notice how the number of orthogonal beam pairs increases with N_x . To determine the beam ranges that ensure the beam orthogonality, we express the solution (17) in terms of $z_{\text{max}}, z_{\text{max,ref}}$, using (15b), i.e.

$$z_{\text{max}} = \frac{N_x z_{\text{max,ref}}}{N_x + \frac{8\pi}{kd_x} \frac{z_{\text{max,ref}}}{N_x d_x} p}. \quad (18)$$

Essentially, for each choice of $z_{\text{max,ref}}$, (18) defines a set of beams that are all orthogonal to the reference. This is demonstrated in Fig.3(b), where $C_L(0, w_z)$ is plotted as a function of $z_{\text{max,ref}}, z_{\text{max}}$, for an array of size $N_x = 500$.

2) *Beams with $w_\theta \neq 0$ and $w_z = 0$* : This case corresponds to beams that propagate along different directions, $\theta \neq \theta_{\text{ref}}$, with the same beam range (zero beam range detuning), $z_{\text{max}} = z_{\text{max,ref}}$. For $w_z = 0$, the summation in (14) becomes

$$C_L(w_\theta, 0) = \left| \frac{1}{N_x} \sum_{n_x} e^{jw_\theta n_x} \right| = \left| \frac{\sin\left(\frac{N_x}{2} w_\theta\right)}{N_x \sin\left(\frac{1}{2} w_\theta\right)} \right|. \quad (19)$$

The solutions of equation $C_L(w_\theta, 0) = 0$ satisfy

$$w_\theta = \frac{2\pi q}{N_x}, \quad (20)$$

where $q \in \mathbb{Z}$, with $q \neq 0, \pm N_x, \pm 2N_x, \dots$, to exclude the nulls of the denominator that lead to $C_L(w_\theta, 0) = 1$. While w_θ can mathematically acquire any value, it corresponds to angular range and, according to (15a), it cannot exceed $2kd_x$. This translates into $|q| \leq N_x kd_x/\pi$, and hence $0 < |q| \leq N_x kd_x/\pi$.

In Fig.3(c) we plot $C_L(w_\theta, 0)$ as a function of the array size N_x and the normalized detuning parameter $\sin \theta - \sin \theta_{\text{ref}} = -w_\theta/kd_x$. To determine the beam directions that ensure the beam orthogonality, we express the solution (20) in terms of $\theta, \theta_{\text{ref}}$, using (15a), i.e.

$$\theta = \arcsin\left(\sin \theta_{\text{ref}} - \frac{2\pi q}{N_x kd_x}\right). \quad (21)$$

For each choice of θ_{ref} , (21) defines a set of beams that are all orthogonal to the reference. This is demonstrated in Fig.3(d), where $C_L(w_\theta, 0)$ is plotted as a function of $\theta_{\text{ref}}, \theta$, for an array of size $N_x = 500$.

3) *Beams with $w_\theta \neq 0$ and $w_z \neq 0$* : Performing the summation in (14) leads to the analytical result

$$C_L(w_\theta, w_z) = \frac{1}{N_x} \frac{\sqrt{C_A + C_B + C_C}}{|\cos w_z - \cos w_\theta|}, \quad (22)$$

where the terms C_A, C_B, C_C are given explicitly by

$$C_A = (\cos w_\theta - \cos w_z) (\cos(N_x w_\theta) - 1), \quad (23a)$$

$$C_B = 2(\cos w_z - 1) (\cos w_\theta + 1) \left(\cos \frac{N_x w_z}{2} \cos \frac{N_x w_\theta}{2} - 1 \right), \quad (23b)$$

$$C_C = -2 \sin w_z \sin w_\theta \sin \frac{N_x w_z}{2} \sin \frac{N_x w_\theta}{2}. \quad (23c)$$

For either $w_\theta = 0$ or $w_z = 0$, it is straightforward to verify that (22) reduces to (16) and (19), respectively. In the most general case, where $w_\theta \neq 0, w_z \neq 0$, the nulls of (22), can be found with simple inspection of the factorized form of terms C_A, C_B, C_C . Nulls of the numerator that occur with nulls of the denominator lead to nonzero correlation and, hence, it is required that the $|\cos w_z - \cos w_\theta|$ term remains nonzero when we are looking for the nulls of the sum $C_A + C_B + C_C$. With simple inspection of term C_A , the requirement for $C_A = 0$ and nonzero denominator leads to $N_x w_\theta = 2\pi q$, which is no other than the condition (20), previously found for the special case

Figure 4. Correlation of cosine beams, as a function of the detuning parameters $\sin\theta - \sin\theta_{\text{ref}} = -w_\theta/kd_x$ and $\beta_x - \beta_{x,\text{ref}} = w_z/kd_x$, for a ULA with $N_x = 500$ elements. The zeros and poles of C_L given by (20), (25) and (26), respectively, are shown explicitly in a small region around $w_\theta = 0, w_z = 0$. The dashed lines mark the cross-sections at the characteristic detunings $w_\theta = 0$ (right panel) and $w_z = 0$ (bottom panel). The color plots are depicted in log scale, to emphasize the details.

of $w_z = 0$. This condition leads also to $C_C = 0$ and, hence, (22) reduces to

$$C_L = \frac{\sqrt{2(\cos w_z - 1) \left(\cos \frac{2\pi q}{N_x} + 1 \right) \left((-1)^q \cos \frac{N_x w_z}{2} - 1 \right)}}{N_x \left| \cos w_z - \cos \frac{2\pi q}{N_x} \right|}. \quad (24)$$

The nulls of C_L can be found by individually setting to zero each of the three factors in the numerator of (24). Earlier we found that $w_z < kd_x$, which for typical $\lambda/2$ spacing translates into $w_z < \pi$. Hence, the first factor in the numerator is always nonzero, except for $w_z = 0$. As a result, the nulls are primarily

Table I
SUMMARY OF COSINE BEAM ORTHOGONALITY CONDITIONS

Beam detunings	Beam directions	Beam ranges	Orthogonal beam enumeration
$w_\theta = 0, w_z \neq 0$	$\theta = \theta_{\text{ref}}$	$z_{\text{max}}: (18)$	$0 < p < \frac{N_x kd_x}{4\pi}$
$w_\theta \neq 0, w_z = 0$	$\theta: (21)$	$z_{\text{max}} = z_{\text{max,ref}}$	$0 < q < N_x \frac{kd_x}{\pi}$
$w_\theta \neq 0, w_z \neq 0$	$\theta: (21)$	$z_{\text{max}}: (27)$	all p, q except: (26)

determined by the last factor, and are given by

$$w_z = \begin{cases} \frac{2\pi}{N_x} 2p, & q : \text{even} \\ \frac{2\pi}{N_x} (2p \pm 1), & q : \text{odd} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

with

$$q \neq \begin{cases} 2p, & q : \text{even} \\ 2p \pm 1, & q : \text{odd} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

where $p, q \in \mathbb{Z}$ and (26) excludes the nulls of the denominator (poles of C_L) that lead to nonzero C_L . Hence, under the constraint (26), all beams with w_θ given by (20) and w_z given by (25) guarantee that $C_L = 0$. The corresponding beam directions are given by (21). To determine the beam ranges, we express (25) in terms of $z_{\text{max}}, z_{\text{max,ref}}$, using (15b), i.e.

$$z_{\text{max}} = \begin{cases} \frac{N_x z_{\text{max,ref}}}{N_x + \frac{4\pi}{kd_x} \frac{z_{\text{max,ref}}}{N_x} 2p}, & q : \text{even} \\ \frac{N_x z_{\text{max,ref}}}{N_x + \frac{4\pi}{kd_x} \frac{z_{\text{max,ref}}}{N_x} (2p \pm 1)}. & q : \text{odd} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

As an example, in Fig. 4, the beam correlations are shown for a ULA with $N_x = 500$, as a function of the detunings $\sin\theta - \sin\theta_{\text{ref}} = -w_\theta/kd_x$ and $\beta_x - \beta_{x,\text{ref}} = w_z/kd_x$. The zeros and poles of C_L given by (20), (25) and (26), respectively, are shown explicitly in a small region around $w_\theta = 0, w_z = 0$, together with cross-sections at the characteristic detunings $w_\theta = 0$ (right panel) and $w_z = 0$ (bottom panel).

All findings are summarized in Table I. The first column lists the three cases. The second and third columns describe explicitly the beam properties that ensure orthogonality for each case, in terms of the detunings (15a), (15b). The last column lists the number of orthogonal beams for each case: For the first case ($w_\theta = 0$), the integer p enumerates how many beams with z_{max} given by (18) are orthogonal to beams with a chosen $z_{\text{max,ref}}$. For the second case ($w_z = 0$), the integer q enumerates how many beams with θ given by (21) are orthogonal to beams with a chosen θ_{ref} . Last, for the general case ($w_\theta \neq 0, w_z \neq 0$), the integers p, q are defined from the previous two cases, with the exception of the marked values.

B. Beam correlations at the Rx

In this section we verify that the beam orthogonality engineered at the Tx is preserved at the Rx. To this end, we propagate the beams numerically and we apply (7) at the Rx.

First, we consider a Tx consisting of $N_x = 1000$ elements and a Rx of the same size, located at $x_R = 0, z_R = 10\text{m}$. For the reference beam we use $z_{\text{max,ref}} = 20\text{m}$ and we use a tunable beam to scan z_{max} , as shown schematically in Fig. 5(a). In Fig. 5(b) we plot (22) (cyan solid line), i.e., the analytical correlation of the two beams at the Tx, and we also plot the

Figure 5. Beam orthogonality at the Rx. (a) Schematic illustration of two cosine beams generated by a Tx of size $N_x = 1000$ and directed towards the Rx, located at $(x_R, 0, z_R)$. The reference beam has $z_{\max, \text{ref}} = 20$ m and, for the tunable beam, z_{\max} accounts for a multitude of cosine beams. In this example $\theta = \theta_{\text{ref}} = 0^\circ$. (b) Beam correlation at the Tx and the Rx, as a function of z_{\max} , for Rx of size $N_x = 1000$ located at $(x_R = 0 \text{ m}, 0, z_R = 10 \text{ m})$. (c) Beam correlation as a function of the Rx size. The dashed line marks the cross-section shown in (b). (d) Beam correlation as a function of the Rx displacement along z ($x_R = 0 \text{ m}$) for Rx size $N_x = 1000$. (e) Beam correlation as a function of the Rx displacement along x ($z_R = 10 \text{ m}$) for Rx size $N_x = 1000$.

numerically calculated correlation of the two beams at the Rx (black dashed line), as a function of z_{\max} . As predicted by our analytical formulas, within the examined parametric space, eight beams are found to satisfy $C_L = 0$, all orthogonal to the reference beam. Their orthogonality is successfully retrieved at the Rx, verifying the predictions of (5).

Next, in Fig. 5(c), we study the impact of the Rx size on the retrieved beam orthogonality. As predicted by the derivation of (7), for small Rx panels where the beams are only partially

captured by the Rx, the orthogonality is not retrieved correctly. However, with increasing Rx size, the received beams end up being entirely captured by the Rx, and the correlations converge to their analytical predictions. In fact, beyond a certain Rx size (here equal to the Tx size), the retrieved correlations do not change, i.e. it suffices for the Rx panel to have the same size as the Tx.

Last, in Fig. 5(d) and Fig. 5(e) we test the retrieved orthogonality against longitudinal and lateral displacements, respectively, of the Rx. Due to the elongated shape of the beam, there is a large range of Rx positions along the z -axis, where the orthogonality is preserved; this property is crucial, as it ensures the beam orthogonality for users residing *anywhere along the beam path*. In essence, two beams, selected from the orthogonal cosine beamset and dedicated to two different users, are always orthogonal regardless of the exact location of the users, which can move along the beam path. In turn, the correlations are more sensitive to lateral displacements and can be compensated with larger Rx panels. Also, the Rx does not necessarily have to be exactly parallel to the Tx. The additional phase accumulated by the propagated beams, due to possible tilt of the Rx, is common to all and is canceled out when performing their inner product (except for relatively large tilts, in which case the beam might not be captured entirely by the Rx, leading to poor retrieval of beam orthogonality). Importantly, our findings demonstrate that multiple users can be located anywhere in the near-field, possibly moving, and simultaneously communicating without interference; by assigning different beams to different users, the concept of SDMA is brought to the near-field, hence the term NF-SDMA.

IV. COSINE BEAMS WITH UPA'S

In this section, we extend the previous analysis from ULAs to UPAs. The UPA is centered at the origin of the coordinate system, extends on the xy -plane, and consists of $N_x \times N_y$ elements that are arranged with periodicity d_x and d_y along the x and y directions, respectively. The UPA generates beams with tailored amplitude and phase characteristics that propagate in the $z > 0$ semi-infinite space. The E -field profile at the input plane ($z = 0$) has the form

$$E(x, y, 0) = A(x, y)e^{j\phi(x, y)}. \quad (28)$$

For cosine beams, the phase profile (9) is generalized to two dimensions as

$$\phi(x, y) = kx \sin \theta \cos \varphi + ky \sin \theta \sin \varphi - k\beta_x |x| - k\beta_y |y|, \quad (29)$$

where the angles θ, φ account for the steering direction. The parameters β_x, β_y are expressed as

$$\beta_x = \frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max, x}}, \quad (30a)$$

$$\beta_y = \frac{N_y d_y}{2z_{\max, y}}, \quad (30b)$$

where $z_{\max, x}$ and $z_{\max, y}$ is the beam range on the xz and yz plane, respectively. Without loss of generality we will consider beams with $z_{\max, x} = z_{\max, y} \equiv z_{\max}$.

To derive the condition for beam orthogonality, we discretize the continuous phase on the UPA grid, i.e. we express (29) at points $x = n_x d_x, y = n_y d_y$, where

$$n_x = -\frac{N_x - 1}{2}, -\frac{N_x - 1}{2} + 1, \dots, \frac{N_x - 1}{2}, \quad (31a)$$

$$n_y = -\frac{N_y - 1}{2}, -\frac{N_y - 1}{2} + 1, \dots, \frac{N_y - 1}{2}. \quad (31b)$$

The correlation of steering vectors for two beams characterized by $(\theta, \varphi, z_{\max})$ and $(\theta_{\text{ref}}, \varphi_{\text{ref}}, z_{\max, \text{ref}})$, respectively, is formulated as

$$C_P(w_{\theta_x}, w_{\theta_y}, w_{z_x}, w_{z_y}) = \left| \frac{1}{N_x N_y} \sum_{n_x} \sum_{n_y} e^{jw_{\theta_x} n_x} e^{jw_{\theta_y} n_y} e^{jw_{z_x} |n_x|} e^{jw_{z_y} |n_y|} \right|, \quad (32)$$

where the subscript P indicates that the correlation function refers to planar arrays. The parameters involved are defined as

$$w_{\theta_x} = kd_x (\sin \theta_{\text{ref}} \cos \varphi_{\text{ref}} - \sin \theta \cos \varphi), \quad (33a)$$

$$w_{\theta_y} = kd_y (\sin \theta_{\text{ref}} \sin \varphi_{\text{ref}} - \sin \theta \sin \varphi), \quad (33b)$$

$$w_{z_x} = kd_x (\beta_x - \beta_{x, \text{ref}}) = kd_x \left(\frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max}} - \frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max, \text{ref}}} \right), \quad (33c)$$

$$w_{z_y} = kd_y (\beta_y - \beta_{y, \text{ref}}) = kd_y \left(\frac{N_y d_y}{2z_{\max}} - \frac{N_y d_y}{2z_{\max, \text{ref}}} \right). \quad (33d)$$

Because the contributions of the x and y components to the sum (32) are independent, we may group the summation as

$$C_P(w_{\theta_x}, w_{\theta_y}, w_{z_x}, w_{z_y}) = \left| \left(\frac{1}{N_x} \sum_{n_x} e^{jw_{\theta_x} n_x} e^{jw_{z_x} |n_x|} \right) \left(\frac{1}{N_y} \sum_{n_y} e^{jw_{\theta_y} n_y} e^{jw_{z_y} |n_y|} \right) \right|, \quad (34)$$

which is simply written in terms of C_L , the correlation function for ULA's, as

$$C_P(w_{\theta_x}, w_{\theta_y}, w_{z_x}, w_{z_y}) = C_L(w_{\theta_x}, w_{z_x}) C_L(w_{\theta_y}, w_{z_y}). \quad (35)$$

For steering on the xz -plane we set $\varphi = \varphi_{\text{ref}} = 0^\circ$, which leads to $w_{\theta_x} = w_\theta$ and $w_{\theta_y} = 0$.

For $\beta_y = 0$ we can shape beams that converge along the x -direction and are invariant along the y -direction, i.e. 1D cosine beams, using the entire two-dimensional (2D) surface of the UPA, as we schematically show in Fig. 6(a), left panel. In Fig. 6(b) we demonstrate the numerical propagation of a 1D beam with $\theta = \varphi = 0^\circ$ and $z_{\max} = 20$ m. Note that, for steering on the xz -plane ($w_{\theta_y} = 0$) of beams with $w_{z_y} = 0$, $C_L(w_{\theta_y}, w_{z_y}) = C_L(0, 0) = 1$, i.e. the correlation function C_P of 1D cosine beams reduces to that of a ULA. Hence, with UPAs, all the conclusions previously drawn about beam orthogonality in ULA's hold here as well. Importantly, due to the 2D nature of UPAs, the beam divergence in the y -direction is significantly reduced with respect to ULAs, as verified in the snapshots shown in Fig. 6(b); the beam is concentrated within a narrow aperture, maximizing the power at the Rx that resides in its near-field (the Fraunhofer distance in this example is 250 m).

For $\beta_y \neq 0$ we take full advantage of the 2D nature of UPAs to form 2D cosine beams, i.e. beams that converge on both the

Figure 6. Generation of orthogonal cosine beams with UPA's. (a) Schematic representation of outer rays for the generation of 1D (left) and 2D (right) beams. Numerical propagation of (b) 1D and (c) 2D beam, with $z_{\max} = 20$ m, using a UPA with 500×500 elements.

xz and yz planes, as we schematically show in Fig. 6(a), right panel. In Fig. 6(c) we demonstrate the numerical propagation of such a beam that bears all the properties of 1D cosine beams and also has the advantage of independently controlling the beam orthogonality in the two transverse planes.

V. CODEBOOK DESIGN FOR MULTI-ANTENNA RXS

To design codebooks for multiple access, we need to construct sets of orthogonal beams. In Section III-A, we established the conditions that ensure the orthogonality between beam pairs. Next, we study whether these conditions can ensure the orthogonality between all beams of the same set.

A. Beam orthogonality and mode enumeration

1) *Beams with $w_\theta = 0$ and $w_z \neq 0$* : For zero angular detuning, we showed that (18) defines a set of beams that are all orthogonal to a chosen reference beam. To investigate whether the orthogonality holds among any pair belonging to the same beamset (among different values of z_{\max} for the chosen $z_{\max, \text{ref}}$), we randomly choose two beams A and B from

the beamset. Each beam is orthogonal to the reference beam, hence from (18) it holds that

$$kd_x \left(\frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max,A}} - \frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max,\text{ref}}} \right) = \frac{4\pi p_A}{N_x}, \quad (36a)$$

$$kd_x \left(\frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max,B}} - \frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max,\text{ref}}} \right) = \frac{4\pi p_B}{N_x}, \quad (36b)$$

where p_A and p_B are two different integers. Eliminating $z_{\max,\text{ref}}$ from (36a),(36b) leads to

$$kd_x \left(\frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max,A}} - \frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max,B}} \right) = \frac{4\pi(p_A - p_B)}{N_x}, \quad (37)$$

where $p_A - p_B$ is also an integer and, therefore, beams A and B also satisfy (18). Because beams A and B are different, $p_A - p_B$ is nonzero, ensuring that the denominator in (16) is nonzero, i.e. $C_L = 0$. As a result, because the chosen beams can be any pair belonging to the beamset, it is ensured that all beams are orthogonal.

We can now construct a relevant codebook, which we denote as $\text{CB}p$. First, we choose the common direction $\theta = \theta_{\text{ref}}$ for all beams, and next, we choose a reference $z_{\max,\text{ref}}$ in (18), to calculate the cosine beam range z_{\max} of all beams belonging to the codebook. Different choice of the reference $z_{\max,\text{ref}}$ and/or the angle θ , leads to a different beamset, i.e. to a different version of codebook $\text{CB}p$.

To enumerate the beams of $\text{CB}p$, we can take into account that, to capture a beam efficiently, the Rx must reside within the beam range, i.e. $z_R \leq z_{\max,\text{ref}}, z_{\max}$. Without loss of generality, the reference beam can always satisfy this condition by choosing $z_{\max,\text{ref}} \rightarrow \infty$. The maximum integer, $p_{\max} = \max(|p|)$ that satisfies $z_R \leq z_{\max}$ is then found by solving (18) in terms of p , and is given by

$$p_{\max} = \left\lfloor \frac{kd_x d_x N_x^2}{\pi 8z_R} \right\rfloor, \quad (38)$$

yielding a total of p_{\max} orthogonal beams ($p = 1, 2, \dots, p_{\max}$), i.e. communication modes. Examples are presented in Fig. 7(a).

2) *Beams with $w_\theta \neq 0$ and $w_z = 0$* : Following similar steps, it is straightforward to show that all beams belonging to the beamset (21), having the same z_{\max} and different θ , are orthogonal.

To construct a codebook with such beams, first we choose the common z_{\max} , and next, we choose a reference θ_{ref} in (21), to calculate the direction θ of all beams belonging to the codebook, which we denote as $\text{CB}q$. Different choice of the reference θ_{ref} and/or the range z_{\max} , leads to a different beamset, i.e. to a different version of codebook $\text{CB}q$.

The number of all possible beam directions depends on the maximum chosen angle, θ_{\max} . Without loss of generality, we may set $\theta_{\text{ref}} = 0$ for the reference beam, and identify all beam directions θ contained within $[-\theta_{\max}, \theta_{\max}]$. The maximum integer, $q_{\max} = \max(|q|)$, that satisfies $|\theta| \leq \theta_{\max}$ is found by solving (21) in terms of q , and is given by

$$q_{\max} = \left\lfloor \sin(\theta_{\max}) \frac{N_x kd_x}{2\pi} \right\rfloor, \quad (39)$$

Figure 7. Maximum number of communication modes for codebooks $\text{CB}p$ and $\text{CB}q$, as a function of the array size. (a) $\text{CB}p$: modes per minimum beam range and examples for $z_{\max} > z_R = 5\text{m}, 10\text{m}, 20\text{m}$. (b) $\text{CB}q$: modes per maximum steering angle and examples for $|\theta| \leq \theta_{\max} = 0.2^\circ, 1^\circ, 5^\circ$. The orange dot marks the case for $N_x = 500$ and $z_R = 10\text{m}$, $\theta_{\max} = 1^\circ$.

yielding a total of $2q_{\max} + 1$ orthogonal beams ($q = -q_{\max}, \dots, 0, \dots, q_{\max}$), i.e. communication modes. Examples are presented in Fig. 7(b).

3) *Beams with generalized w_θ, w_z* : In the most general case, where beams can be directed towards different angles with different beam ranges, we can first identify the possible beam directions, using (21). For example, for a reference beam with $\theta_{\text{ref}} = 0^\circ, z_{\max,\text{ref}} \rightarrow \infty$, the set of orthogonal beam directions is given by the angles

$$\theta = \arcsin \left(\frac{2\pi q}{N_x kd_x} \right), \quad (40)$$

with $q = -q_{\max}, \dots, 0, \dots, q_{\max}$ and q_{\max} given by (39). Then, for each angle we can specify the orthogonal beam ranges, using (27) with $z_{\max,\text{ref}} \rightarrow \infty$. In this case, the set of orthogonal beam ranges is given by the distances

$$z_{\max} = \begin{cases} \frac{kd_x d_x N_x^2}{\pi 8p}, & q : \text{even} \\ \frac{kd_x d_x N_x^2}{\pi 4(2p-1)}, & q : \text{odd} \end{cases} \quad (41)$$

with

$$p_{\max} \begin{cases} \left\lfloor \frac{kd_x d_x N_x^2}{\pi 8z_R} \right\rfloor, & q : \text{even} \\ \left\lfloor \frac{kd_x d_x N_x^2}{\pi 8z_R} + \frac{1}{2} \right\rfloor, & q : \text{odd} \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

with $p = 1, 2, \dots, p_{\max}$. Note that, in the lower branch of (41) we have preserved only the “-” sign. The reason is that both signs lead to the same solution set with enumeration starting from $p = 0$ for the “+” sign and from $p = 1$ for the “-” sign. The “-” sign ensures common enumeration in both branches with $p > 0$.

As a result, the maximum number of communication modes, M_{\max} , for a certain choice of p_{\max}, q_{\max} is

$$M_{\max} = p_{\max}(2q_{\max} + 1). \quad (43)$$

Note, however, that the beams defined by directions (40) and ranges (41) are not necessarily all orthogonal with each other. Therefore, the number of communication modes is less

Figure 8. Codebook design examples. (a) Schematic representation of possible communication modes (dots) for Tx size of $N_x = 500$. The solid lines represent the steering directions, and the horizontal dashed lines mark the cosine beam ranges (magenta for q :even, green for q :odd). The striped area denotes the zone where multiple RxS are located. Examples of communication modes, using codebook (b) CB_p ($w_\theta = 0$), (c) CB_q ($w_z = 0$), (d) CB_{pq} with modes on q :even, and (e) CB_{pq} with modes on q of mixed parity. Each triangle depicts the spatial distribution of the corresponding cosine beam of each mode.

than M_{\max} , i.e. (40), (41) are necessary, though not sufficient conditions. We can now select a random pair of two such beams, A and B, to examine their orthogonality. From (40) we choose two random angles, characterized by the integers q_A and q_B , and from (41) we choose two random ranges, characterized by the integers p_A and p_B . In terms of the integers q, p that enumerate the angles and ranges, beam A is characterized by q_A, p_A and beam B by q_B, p_B . Using (22) with the chosen parameters inserted in (15a) and (15b), leads to the following conditions for beam orthogonality

$$w_z = \begin{cases} \frac{4\pi}{N_x}(p_A - p_B), & q_A - q_B : \text{even}, \\ \frac{4\pi}{N_x}(p_A - p_B + \frac{1}{2}), & q_A - q_B : \text{odd}, \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

with

$$|q_A - q_B| \neq \begin{cases} 2|p_A - p_B|, & q_A - q_B : \text{even}, \\ 2|p_A - p_B + \frac{1}{2}|, & q_A - q_B : \text{odd}. \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

Because the difference of any two even or odd integers is always an even integer, the condition " $q_A - q_B$: even" refers to any beams on directions defined by (40) with either even or odd q . Similarly, the condition " $q_A - q_B$: odd" refers to any pair of beams, with q of mixed parity. Using (40), (41) with the exception of beams in (45), we can now construct a relevant codebook, which we denote as CB_{pq} .

As an example, let us define the communication modes within a narrow angular range of 1° , for users residing up to $z_R = 10\text{m}$ away from the Tx, which is equipped with a ULA of size $N_x = 500$. Setting $z_R = 10\text{m}$ in (38) and $\theta_{\max} = 1^\circ$ in (39), leads to $p_{\max} = 3$ and $2q_{\max} + 1 = 9$, also marked in Fig. 7 with the orange dot. Hence, there is a maximum of $M_{\max} = 27$ possible communication modes, corresponding to the steering directions with $q = -4, \dots, +4$ and beam ranges with $p = 1, 2, 3$, as schematically shown in Fig. 8(a). The magenta (green) lines denote that q is even (odd). Each magenta/green dot denotes one such mode, which is associated with a single (q, p) pair; in essence, the dots mark the tip of each cosine beam that corresponds to the specific mode, as determined by the outer rays (see Fig. 2). The striped area marks the region where all users are located. Examples of sets of communication modes are depicted in Figs. 8(b)-(e), also showing the corresponding cosine beam range of each mode, which is contained in the triangular region of each mode. Fig. 8(b) depicts all possible communication modes of codebook CB_p for common angle $q = 2$, and cosine beam ranges $p = 1, 2, 3$. In this case, three users residing in the striped area are served individually by the three cosine beams, schematically shown as colored triangles. Fig. 8(c) depicts five communication modes of codebook CB_q serving five users, for common cosine beam range $p = 1$ and angles $q = -4, -2, 0, 2, 4$. In Fig. 8(d) three modes of codebook CB_{pq} all reside on steering angles with q :even, and are characterized by $(q = -4, p = 2)$, $(q = 0, p = 1)$ and $(q = 2, p = 3)$. Last, in Fig. 8(e) four modes of codebook CB_{pq} reside on steering angles of mixed parity, and are characterized by $(q = -3, p = 2)$, $(q = 0, p = 2)$, $(q = 3, p = 3)$ and $(q = 4, p = 1)$.

B. Performance analysis

To evaluate the performance of the proposed beams, consider a Tx generating M beams, to simultaneously serve M users. An example for $M = 2$ is shown schematically in Fig. 9(a). The two users are located anywhere within the zone marked with the striped pattern. They reside on the z -axis, and multiple access becomes particularly challenging, because the beams have to be co-linear. The relevant codebook is CB_p , which we will use to construct orthogonal beams with common $\theta = 0^\circ$. One beam is dedicated to user #1, a second beam is dedicated to user #2, and their z_{\max} values are chosen so as to minimize the beam correlations. The Tx and users are each equipped with a ULA consisting of $N_x = 1000$ elements. The calculated beam correlations are presented in Fig. 9(a), showing the first six nulls that define six orthogonal beams. For $M = 2$ we choose the values denoted as $z_{\max,1}, z_{\max,2}$ to construct two cosine beams, although any other of the nulls could be used as well.

Figure 9. NF-SDMA for multi-antenna Rx with cosine beams, and comparison with focused beams. Beam correlations for (a) cosine and (b) focused beams, generated by a ULA with $N_x = 1000$ elements. Average spectral efficiency for (c) two, (d) four and (e) six users. The users reside in the region shown with the striped pattern in (a),(b), 5–20 m in front of the Tx. The blue/gray insets denote the cosine/focused beams, respectively.

As benchmark, we will compare the performance of the cosine beams with that of focused beams, generated by the same ULA. For beam-focusing along the direction θ on the xz -plane, the ULA phase must be of the form [4], [5]

$$\phi(x) = -kx \sin \theta + k \frac{x^2 \cos^2 \theta}{2f_0}, \quad (46)$$

where $x = n_x d_x$. The beam correlations for beam-focusing with $\theta = 0^\circ$ are calculated numerically using (46), and are presented in Fig. 9(b). As expected [35]–[37], the beam correlations do not become zero, rather acquire local minima. The first six minima define six focused beams with minimum correlation and, to construct two focused beam, we choose the values denoted as $f_{0,1}, f_{0,2}$.

To evaluate the performance of the chosen beams we use the receive signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) per Rx as a performance metric, which is given by (see Appendix D for details)

$$\text{SINR}_m = \frac{\iint |E_m|^2}{|\sum_{l \neq m} \iint E_l E_m^*| + P_v}, \quad (47)$$

where P_v is the noise power, and $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$. The receive SINR at each Rx is related to its achievable rate as

$$R_m = \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_m), \quad (48)$$

and the overall spectral efficiency (SE) is expressed as $R = \sum_m R_m$. Averaging over all possible user locations leads to the average SE, $\langle R \rangle = \sum_m \langle R_m \rangle$.

In Fig. 9(c) the performance of both cosine (solid blue

line) and focused (solid gray line) beams is evaluated as a function of the signal-to-noise-ratio, $\text{SNR} = 10 \log_{10}(P_m/P_v)$, where $P_m = \iint E_m E_m^*$ is the signal power. The dashed line marks the maximum achievable $\langle R \rangle$, which corresponds to zero interference, in which case $\text{SINR} \equiv \text{SNR}$. In this example the two users reside anywhere within 5–20 m in front of the Tx, and the cosine beams clearly outperform the focused beams for a wide SNR range.

In Fig. 9(d) the calculations are repeated for $M = 4$ users, residing anywhere within the same zone. In this case, four beams are designed according to the first four calculated minima shown in Fig. 9(a),(b). Similarly, in Fig. 9(e) the calculations are repeated for $M = 6$ users and six beams. With increasing number of users the SE improves dramatically with cosine beams, contrary to focused beams, for which the SE saturates for substantially lower SNR levels.

VI. CODEBOOK DESIGN FOR SINGLE ANTENNA RXS

Single-antenna Rx probe the incoming wave only at a single point and, hence, an inner product is not applicable; the suppression of interference relies entirely on the absence of other waves. In this case beam orthogonality can be defined similarly to classical SDMA, where a peak in one beam at the location of the Rx coincides with the nulls of all other beams. For conventional beams, because their propagation in the near-field is accompanied by intensity oscillations that change qualitatively with the propagation distance, classical SDMA fails. Note, however, that because cosine beams are characterized by a standing wave pattern that extends across the entire cosine beam range, their near-field is predictable and can be tailored to promote or suppress the beam intensity at selected regions. Hence, it is possible to design codebooks, where the intensity at the maximum of one beam overlaps with zeros from all the other beams of the codebook. This possibility essentially brings the classical SDMA in the near-field, which is an ideal scheme for Rx equipped with single antennas, instead of arrays.

The standing wave that is formed in a cosine beam with parameter β_x has the form $\cos^2(k\beta_x x)$ and extends up to the corresponding z_{\max} . Mathematically, a perfect standing wave requires two counter-propagating plane waves of infinite extent. However, due to the finite size of the Tx, the cosine wave is formed by a truncated version of those waves, and the finite aperture of the Tx introduces an envelope that suppresses the peaks of the standing wave towards the edges [46]. Depending on the ratio of z_{\max} relative to the size of the array, which is expressed via β_x , the envelope can controllably shrink, in turn suppressing the peaks of the standing wave. In fact, at $z = z_{\max}/2$, the two waves interfere across the entire beam cross-section, forming a standing wave of $N_x d_x/2$ extent, beyond which the beam intensity quickly decays to zero (see Fig. 2). The first zeros of $\cos^2(k\beta_x x)$ occur at $x = \pm \pi/(2k\beta_x)$. To suppress interference with beams at other angles we tune the first zeros of the standing wave to occur at $x = \pm N_x d_x/2$, leading to

$$z_{\max} = \frac{(N_x d_x)^2}{\lambda} \equiv \frac{z_F}{2}, \quad (49)$$

Figure 10. Near-field beam orthogonality for single antenna Rxs. (a) Schematic illustration of two uncorrelated beams, in classical far-field SDMA (left) and in NF-SDMA (right). (b) Beam correlations as a function of the tunable beam's steering angle θ , for reference beam with $\theta_{ref} = 0^\circ$. For NF-SDMA the beam range is $z_{max} = 20$ m (c) Beam intensity at $z = z_F/4 = 10$ m, as a function of the observation angle, θ_{obs} . The ULA consists of 200 elements (with $\lambda/2$ spacing), and the Fraunhofer distance is 40 m.

where z_F is the Fraunhofer distance. Probing the beam at $z = z_{max}/2$ translates to $z = z_F/4$, which resides in the radiating near-field.

To construct a codebook, first we use (49) to select the common z_{max} , and next, we choose a reference θ_{ref} in (21), to calculate the direction θ of all beams belonging to the codebook. Note that the steering angles in (21) are also the steering angles in typical SDMA. This is a direct consequence of the fact that cosine beams are formed by a pair of counter-propagating waves, i.e. they are linear superposition of the beams used in SDMA. As such, they bear the same angular correlation properties.

In Fig. 10 we present one codebook design for our proposed NF-SDMA scheme, which we compare with the classical far-field SDMA. Schematic representations of both schemes are shown in Fig. 10(a), where two beams are depicted, one reference beam directed towards $\theta_{ref} = 0^\circ$ and one beam with tunable direction θ . The Tx has size $N_x = 200$, for which $z_F = 40$ m. Following the preceding analysis we use $z_{max} = z_F/2 = 20$ m and we probe the tunable beam at $z = z_F/4 = 10$ m. The beam correlations for both schemes are presented in Fig. 10(b). The dashed colored lines denote the

analytical steering angles predicted by (21), for $q = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$. In Fig. 10(c), cross-sections of the selected beams under both schemes are shown, where the color-code follows that in panel (b). Because all beams are probed deep in the radiating near-field, the local orthogonality in the classical far-field SDMA is lost. On the contrary, with cosine beams, interference is successfully suppressed.

VII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Owing to their localized transverse profile over long distances, cosine beams are ideal resource elements for applications from the near- to the far-field of large radiating apertures. Importantly, the linearity of the phase shifts required to generate these beams, offers to cosine beams a unique advantage over other advanced beam profiles, with respect to the efficiency of their excitation. For example, focused beams require nonlinear phase shifts that can result in very rapid oscillations in ϕ , possibly beyond the resolving capabilities of $\lambda/2$ -spaced array elements. Linear phase shifts are routinely applied in beamformers and RISs and, hence, the technology is well-known and it is straightforward to extend its use for the excitation of cosine beams, and to account for possible real-world factors that might degrade orthogonality, such as imperfect beam shaping, channel impairments, and hardware limitations.

As wireless connectivity is gradually shifting to the near-field or large radiating apertures, the applicability of the classical far-field SDMA becomes questionable. To this end, in this work we introduced the concept of NF-SDMA, to enable multiple access in the near-field. By judicious design, we selected the family of cosine beams as an ideal beamset for realizing NF-SDMA, and we demonstrated that such beams offer the necessary orthogonality (strictly zero correlations) from the near- up to the far-field of the Tx, with respect to all associated parameters, such as the beam direction and beam range. We derived analytically their correlations and demonstrated analytically and verified numerically the plethora of communication modes offered by these beams, for both ULAs and UPAs. Based on our findings, we proposed codebook designs for NF-SDMA, for both multi-antenna and single-antenna Rxs. With our work, we aim to lay the ground for multiple access in the near-field, for 6G wireless connectivity and beyond.

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APPENDIX

A. Beam propagation in k -space

Let us denote as $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{E}(x, y, z)$ the E -field of a beam at the observation point $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)$. The beam propagates along z

and, at $z = 0$ where it is generated by the Tx, its E -field is $\mathbf{E}(x, y, 0) \equiv \mathbf{E}_T(x, y)$. Its two-dimensional Fourier transform is

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}_T(k_x, k_y) = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \mathbf{E}_T(x, y) e^{-j(k_x x + k_y y)} dx dy, \quad (50)$$

where x, y are the Cartesian transverse coordinates and k_x, k_y the corresponding spatial frequencies. Similarly, the inverse Fourier transform reads

$$\mathbf{E}_T(x, y) = \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{\mathbf{E}}_T(k_x, k_y) e^{j(k_x x + k_y y)} dk_x dk_y. \quad (51)$$

Note that the field \mathbf{E}_T and its Fourier transform $\hat{\mathbf{E}}_T$ represent vectors and, hence, the Fourier integrals hold separately for each vector component. The field has to satisfy Maxwell's equations, which for free-space propagation reduce to the vector Helmholtz equation $(\nabla^2 + k^2)\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) = 0$. Expressing similarly at distance z the field $\mathbf{E}(x, y, z)$ via its Fourier transform and inserting it into the Helmholtz equation, we find that the Fourier spectrum $\hat{\mathbf{E}}_R$ of the beam at distance z , where the Rx is located, is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}_R(k_x, k_y; z) = \hat{\mathbf{E}}_T(k_x, k_y) e^{jk_z z}, \quad (52)$$

where $k_z = \sqrt{k^2 - k_x^2 - k_y^2}$ and k is the wavenumber.

B. Input phase for the generation of cosine beams

Cosine beams are generated by two waves with opposite directions. Hence, in the wave representation, the two waves have in-plane k -components of opposite sign, $\pm k_x = \pm k \sin \psi$, where ψ is the angle formed by each ray with respect to the z -axis. The input phase can be written concisely as

$$\phi(x) = k \sin \theta x - k \beta_x |x|, \quad (53)$$

where θ is the steering angle and $\beta_x \equiv \sin \psi$. With simple inspection of Fig. 2, the angle ψ is associated with the ULA size $N_x d_x$ and the beam range z_{\max} as

$$\tan \psi = \frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max}}. \quad (54)$$

Using the trigonometric identity

$$\sin \psi = \frac{\tan \psi}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \psi}}, \quad (55)$$

we find that

$$\beta_x = \frac{\frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max}}}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max}}\right)^2}} \approx \frac{N_x d_x}{2z_{\max}}, \quad (56)$$

for $z_{\max} > N_x d_x$.

C. Correlations of steering vectors at the Tx

The correlation of two beams at the Tx is written as

$$C = \frac{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} E_1(x, y) E_2^*(x, y) dx dy}{\sqrt{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |E_1(x, y)|^2 dx dy} \sqrt{\iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |E_2(x, y)|^2 dx dy}}, \quad (57)$$

where $E_1(x, y) = A_1(x, y) e^{j\phi_1(x, y)}$ and $E_2(x, y) = A_2(x, y) e^{j\phi_2(x, y)}$ are the footprints of the two beams.

For uniform amplitude, $A_1(x, y) = A_2(x, y) \equiv A$, the correlation takes the simpler form

$$C = \frac{\int_{-D_y/2}^{+D_y/2} \int_{-D_x/2}^{+D_x/2} e^{j\phi_1(x, y)} e^{j\phi_2^*(x, y)} dx dy}{D_x D_y}, \quad (58)$$

where integration has been limited within the Tx surface, which has size $D_x \times D_y$, with $D_x = N_x d_x$, $D_y = N_y d_y$. In its discrete version, (58) takes the frequently met form

$$C = \frac{1}{N_x N_y} \sum_{n_x} \sum_{n_y} e^{j\phi_1(n_x d_x, n_y d_y)} e^{j\phi_2^*(n_x d_x, n_y d_y)}. \quad (59)$$

The latter form of C can be equivalently expressed in terms of the corresponding steering vectors, $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2$, where

$$\mathbf{a}_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_x N_y}} \mathbf{a}_{i,y}^T \otimes \mathbf{a}_{i,x}, \quad (60)$$

with $i = 1, 2$, the symbol \otimes denoting the Kronecker product, and

$$\mathbf{a}_{i,x} = \left[e^{j\phi_i(-\frac{N_x-1}{2}, 0)}, e^{j\phi_i(-\frac{N_x-1}{2}+1, 0)}, \dots, e^{j\phi_i(\frac{N_x-1}{2}, 0)} \right], \quad (61a)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_{i,y} = \left[e^{j\phi_i(0, -\frac{N_y-1}{2})}, e^{j\phi_i(0, -\frac{N_y-1}{2}+1)}, \dots, e^{j\phi_i(0, \frac{N_y-1}{2})} \right]. \quad (61b)$$

Using the matrices $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2$ (size $N_x \times N_y$), we may write

$$C = \text{tr}(\mathbf{a}_1^T \mathbf{a}_2^*) = \text{tr}((\mathbf{a}_1^H \mathbf{a}_2)^*) = (\text{tr}(\mathbf{a}_1^H \mathbf{a}_2))^*, \quad (62)$$

where $\text{tr}(\mathbf{a})$ is the trace of matrix \mathbf{a} , $\mathbf{a}\mathbf{b}$ is the matrix product of matrices \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} , and we have taken advantage of the fact that the trace of a square matrix, which is the product of two matrices, can be rewritten as the sum of entry-wise products of their elements. Hence, $|C| = |\text{tr}(\mathbf{a}_1^T \mathbf{a}_2^*)| = |\text{tr}(\mathbf{a}_1^H \mathbf{a}_2)|$.

For ULAs, $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2$ are column matrices and we may simply write $|C| = |(\mathbf{a}_1^T \mathbf{a}_2^*)| = |(\mathbf{a}_1^H \mathbf{a}_2)|$.

D. SINR for multi-antenna Rx

Consider a Tx that transmits multiple beams towards M different Rx. The E -field at the m^{th} Rx will be the superposition of all beams, i.e.

$$E_r = E_1 + E_2 + \dots + E_m + \dots + E_M, \quad (63)$$

where E_m is the E -field of the m^{th} beam that is intended for the m^{th} Rx, and all E_l with $l \neq m$ are interference for the m^{th} Rx. The inner product between the total signal E_r and the desired signal E_m is

$$\iint E_r E_m^* = \iint |E_m|^2 + \sum_{l \neq m} \iint E_l E_m^*, \quad (64)$$

where the integration and summation operations have been interchanged. Note that the first term of the sum in (64) is the power of the signal of interest, while the second term accounts for the interference. Hence, the SINR is written as

$$\text{SINR}_m = \frac{\iint |E_m|^2}{|\sum_{l \neq m} \iint E_l E_m^*| + P_V}. \quad (65)$$

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